

INFLUENCE OF HEAT ON THE CHEMICAL COMPOSITION AND PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF GUM ARABIC

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Gum arabic, heated to 170°, when put into water, swells up to a considerable extent, but does not dissolve and the gel thus formed is non-sticky. There is practically no change in the chemical composition of the gum. The insolubility of the gum at 170° is explained to be due to complete dehydration at this temperature and the consequent removal of protective aqueous films surrounding the micelles or the primary particles of the micelles.

The viscosity of the gum solutions goes on increasing to a great extent as the gum is heated from 100° to 160°. The increase in viscosity is due to the increase of imbibed water in gum micelles. Water appears to be oriented in a shell surrounding the gum micelles and thus the disperse phase becomes highly solvated which results in the increase of viscosity.

Action of NaOH on the gum arabic, heated to different temperatures (110°-170°), has been studied potentiometrically.

Gum arabic, an acid polysaccharide, is mainly a calcium salt of arabic acid, the nucleus of which is aldobionic acid (galactose-glucuronic acid) to which sugar molecules of galactose, arabinose and methylpentose are attached. The structure of the aldobionic acid is given below.

Gum arabic, heated to 170°, when put into water, swells up to a considerable extent, but does not dissolve and the gel thus formed is non-sticky. The object of the present work was to study the change in the chemical composition and physical properties of gum arabic on heating it in dry state to various temperatures above 100° and to investigate the action of NaOH on gum arabic heated to different temperatures (110°-170°) by back potentiometric titrations with 0.02N-HCl.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The gum arabic used for the experiments had the following composition: pentosan, 34.34%; galactan, 33.93%; moisture, 13.53%; calcium, 0.6459%.

Arabic acid was prepared from gum arabic by electro-dialysis through cellophane. The acid thus prepared was dried on a water-bath, powdered and sieved through a fine mesh.

Dilatometer Measurements.—The hydration of gum arabic, heated to different temperatures, was investigated in a dilatometer which is diagrammatically represented in Fig. 1. The tablets were placed in the left part (I) of the dilatometer. The right part (II) was filled with distilled water free from air and CO₂ by turning the three-way tap (b). The dilatometer was then placed in a thermostat to ensure constancy of temperature of $37^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$. After half an hour the left side was evacuated through (e) and afterwards the left part of the dilatometer and part of the capillary (d) were filled with air-free distilled water by opening taps (a) and (b). After closing the three-way tap (b), the dilatometer was ready for measurement and the initial reading on the scale attached to the capillary was immediately taken. The final reading was taken when the level in the capillary was constant for about an hour.

TABLE I

Loss of moisture on heating the gum.

Temp to which the gum was heated ...	110°	120°	130°	140°	150°	160°	170°
% Loss of moisture ...	10.38	11.47	11.94	13.32	13.65	13.65	13.73

TABLE II

Comparative results of the relative viscosity of gum solutions at 37°.

Temp. to which the gum was heated.	Relative viscosity of the gum solutions.					
	6%.	4.5%	3%.	2.5%.	1.5%.	0.75%.
100°	3.480	2.944	2.328	2.087	1.644	1.289
110°	3.772	3.131	2.409	2.168	1.672	1.284
120°	4.018	3.318	2.578	2.306	1.793	1.345
130°	4.13	3.451	2.702	2.418	1.889	1.455
140°	4.415	3.624	2.762	2.478	1.991	1.611
150°	5.998	4.76	3.596	3.174	2.357	1.775

TABLE IIIA

Comparative quantities of 0.02*N*-NaOH required to neutralise the acidity of 25 c.c. of 8% solution of gum, heated to various temperatures, were found by back potentiometric titrations with 0.02*N*-HCl (the p_n values were determined by using hydrogen electrode of the Bunker's type).

Temp. to which gum was heated.	0.02 <i>N</i> -HCl reqd. to neutralise the excess of NaOH.	0.02 <i>N</i> -NaOH reqd. to neutralise the acidity of 2 g. of gum.	Temp. to which gum was heated.	0.02 <i>N</i> -HCl reqd. to neutralise the excess of NaOH.	0.02 <i>N</i> -NaOH reqd. to neutralise the acidity of 2 g. of gum.
110°	19.45 c.c.	4.55 c.c.	150°	14.3 c.c.	10.7 c.c.
120°	19.1	5.9	160°	12.8	12.2
130°	17.45	7.55	170°	10.7	14.3
140°	16.95	8.05			

TABLE IIIB

Arabic acid on drying at 110° becomes insoluble.

Temp. to which arabic acid was heated.	0.1 <i>N</i> -HCl reqd. to neutralise the excess of NaOH.	0.1 <i>N</i> -NaOH reqd. to neutralise the acidity of 2g. of acid.
100° (dehydrated)	7.8 c.c.	17.2 c.c.
170° (")	7.4	17.6

7.8 C.c. of 0.1*N*-HCl are required to neutralise the excess of NaOH, i.e., 17.2 c.c. of 0.1*N*-NaOH neutralise the acidity of 2 g. of arabic acid. The equivalent weight comes out to be 1162 which is quite in agreement with Thomas and Murray (*J. Phys. Chem.* 1928, 32, 676) who found equivalent weight of arabic acid as 1177. The results are also in accordance with Lucien Amy (*Ann. Chim.*, 1934, ix, 2, 287) who found that on dehydration arabic acid was converted into metagummic acid (of about the same acidity) which again was converted into arabic acid on treatment with NaOH.

TABLE IV

Hydration of gum arabic by dilatometer.

Area of the cross section of the capillary = 0.0115 cm.

Temp. to which the gum was heated.	Fall in the capillary per 1 g. of the gum.	Contraction in vol. per 1 g. of the gum.	Temp. to which the gum was heated.	Fall in the capillary per 1 g. of the gum.	Contraction in vol. per 1 g. of the gum.
110°	11.69 cm.	1.345 c.c.	150°	21.78 cm.	2.505 c.c.
120°	13.99	1.609	160°	22.81	2.623
130°	18.67	2.147	170°	24.02	2.763
140°	19.66	2.261			

DISCUSSION

Gum arabic, heated to 170° , when put into water, swells up to a considerable extent, but does not dissolve; the gel thus formed is non-sticky. There is practically no change in the chemical composition of gum arabic on heating it as determined by the estimations of arabinose and galactose. The insolubility of gum in water can be explained to be due to complete dehydration at 170° and the consequent removal of protective aqueous films surrounding the micelles or the primary particles of the micelles, consequently some of the molecules or molecular groups approach so closely that when they are again brought in contact with water, their attraction for water molecules or its ions is unable to separate them. This is similar to the behaviour of gelatin which, when dried at 130° , becomes insoluble due to dehydration. Alexander (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **43**, 438) attributes the insolubility of gelatin to the close approach of its constituent particles.

Insoluble gum swells in water to a jelly-like mass which does not dissolve. According to Procter and Wilson (*J. Phys. Chem.* 1928, **32**, 692) the force which causes swelling of gum is an osmotic force, *i. e.*, the diffusion of water through a membrane. In this case the membrane is the arabate ions or aggregates, and the forces which limit the swelling are the cohesive forces existing between the arabate ions.

It was observed by means of the dilatometer (Table IV) that there is contraction in the total volume of water when the dehydrated gum is brought in contact with water, an evidence that water is imbibed by the gum. The water of this hydration layer has a higher density than free water. Thus the adsorbed water is under a high internal force which is due to the polarising effect of the polar groups of the gum molecules on water dipoles and hence the fall in the capillary of the dilatometer. The first suggestion that water exists in colloids in a state different from that of water, as we know it is in bulk, was made by Balcar, Sansum and Woodyatt (*Arch. Internal. Med.*, 1919, **24**, 116). They suggested a theory that there exists a bound $\rightleftharpoons$ free water equilibrium. On heating, the equilibrium is disturbed, more and more free water is lost with the result that more amount of water will be taken up by gum-micelles that have been heated to higher temperature when placed in contact with water. Svedburg (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **46**, 2673) finds in the case of gelatin that more and more water is taken up by gelatin as the initial content of water in it is low. From our results of dilatometer measurements, we find that the amount of water taken up by gum-micelles goes on increasing with rise of temperature.

Table II (Fig. 2) shows that the viscosity of gum solutions goes on increasing to a great extent as the gum is heated from 100° to 160° . The increase in viscosity may be explained by the fact that viscosity of a solution is a function of the volume of the solute in solution or what is the same thing, a function of free volume of the solvent. The free volume is the difference between the volume occupied by the gum molecules and that of the solution. The increase in the viscosity is therefore perhaps due to increase in imbibed water. Water appears to be oriented in a "shell" surrounding the gum

micelles and thus the disperse phase becomes highly solvated which results in the increase of viscosity. This is in accordance with a view put forward by Gortner that dispersion medium is strongly attracted by the disperse phase, so that the disperse phase

FIG. 2

becomes highly solvated, the particles of disperse phase become surrounded by "shells" of the dispersion medium, the apparent viscosity of the system is greatly increased. This view is further confirmed from the results of dilatometer by means of which we find that volume contractions increase with the temperature to which the gum has been heated.

FIG. 3

Action of NaOH on the gum arabic, heated to different temperatures, 110°-170°, was studied potentiometrically. The quantity of NaOH required for reaching the neutral point goes on increasing with rise of temperature as seen from Table III (Fig. 3). This phenomenon is explained on the basis of difference between the ionisation of calcium and sodium arabates and due to the different hydration of calcium and sodium ions as found by Briggs (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, **35**, 1929) that "with colloids in equilibrium with water, the degree of hydration of the colloid is determined largely, if not entirely, by the number of cations or anions which may be produced from it and that the sodium caseinates are nearly 100 per cent ionised as compared to calcium caseinates which are about 20 per cent ionised". On addition of NaOH, gum arabic, which is a calcium salt of arabic acid, is converted into sodium arabate which gets dissociated to a much greater extent than calcium arabate; hydration of sodium ion being greater than calcium ion, the sodium arabate becomes highly hydrated. Since a lot of water is imbibed by sodium and arabate ions, there is a decrease in free solvent and hence there is an increase in H-ion concentration. The increase in acidity with rise of temperature is due to the fact that on heating, the power to imbibe water goes on increasing as observed from viscosity and dilatometric measurements. Another possible explanation for the increase of acidity of the gum is that the unit of the complex structure of the micelles undergoes a strengthening of cationic linkages releasing bound 'COOH' groups.

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